

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

No9
2025

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 936 sahifa,
2-sentyabr, 2025-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijanovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Woogyu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (Phd)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F.O. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Doniyorov S. M. – "Yangi O'zbekiston" va "Pravda Vostoka" gazetalarini tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F.O. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayova X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the Editorial Board of the newspapers "Yangi Uzbekiston" and "Pravda Vostoka", Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Candidate of Philological Sciences (PhD)

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – doctor of philosophy (PhD) in psychology

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun

Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi” jurnali O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro‘yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha
ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti innovatsion faoliyatini rivojlantirish jarayoni.....	14
Ibragimova Gulsanam Nematovna	
Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining ta'lim metodikasida qo'llanilishi va o'qituvchi kompetentligiga ta'siri	22
Abduyev Sheroz	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda "tabiatshunoslik" fanini raqamli platformalar orqali o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirish: 5e modeli asosida dizayn, baholash va joriy etish.....	25
Ahmadaliyev Shohruh Bahromjon o'g'li	
Ingliz va rus leksikografiyasida o'zbek milliy taom nomlarining lingvistik tahlili	30
Bobojonova Zarina Rashidovna	
Rahbarlarda til bilish darajasi va hissiy intellekt (eq): o'zaro bog'liqlikni o'rganish	34
Isaqulova Baxtigul Xo'jamovna	
Frazeologizmlarni o'rgatishda matn asosida integratsiyalashgan dars modeli: xorijiy til o'rganuvchilar tajribasi	38
Jumayeva Sadbarg Mirolimovna	
O'zbekistonda maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida inklyuziv ta'limni tashkil etishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari: rivojlangan davlatlar tajribasi tahlili	42
Karimova Moxichehra Rixsibayevna	
Rus va ingliz tillarida sharqona realiyalarning leksik-semantik tasnifi	46
Kulmamatova Aziza Do'stmamat qizi	
TRIZ metodikasi asosida texnokratik bolalar bilan ishlash tizimini takomillashtirish	50
Orifjonova Mavludaxon Abduqaxxor qizi	
Raqamli ta'lim muhitida pedagogik kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirish.....	53
Raximberganova Munajat Muzaffar qizi	
Structure of Social Conflict and Stages of its Development	57
Zaynutdinova Shahnoza Yuldashevna	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining ijodiy faoliyatini baholash va rag'batlantirish tizimini takomillashtirish.....	60
Abduraxmonova Nigoraxon Akramali qizi	
Expression of National Mental Characteristics in the Uzbek Lullaby.....	64
Alimbayeva Shaxlo Tursunovna	
Bo'lajak "texnologiya" fani o'qituvchilarini kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlashda kreativ kompetentlikni rivojlantirish tizimining pedagogik zarurati	69
Avazov G'oyibnazar Berdiyevich	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda integratsiyalashgan ta'lim faoliyatini rivojlantirish orqali kommunikativ salohiyatini shakllantirish	72
Baratova Yulduz Asadullayevna	
Umumta'lim maktablarida molekulyar fizikani o'qitishning hozirgi holati	76
Boymirov Sherzod Tuxtayevich, Xudoynazarova Visola Musurmonqul qizi	
Ingliz tilini o'qitishda talabalarning mustaqil ta'lim olish kompetensiyasini akt vositasida rivojlantirish	80
Ergasheva Sevaraxon Ravshanjon qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'lim pedagoglarining kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	84
O'rinova Feruzaxon O'ljayevna, Karimova Gulzodaxon Marufjon qizi	
IIV litsey o'quvchilarining liderlik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning psixologik xususiyatlari.....	90
Gadoyeva Dildora Baxtiyorovna	
Improving the System of Human Resource Capacity Management in Higher Education Institutions: Evidence from Uzbekistan	98
Imomov I., Umirova D.	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida tarbiyalanuvchilarni mantiqiy va tanqidiy fikrlashga o'rgatishning zamonaviy usullari.....	104
Iskandarova Munisa Bahodir qizi	
Tarbiyachi-pedagoglarning emotsional kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish	107
Jovmirzayeva Nargiza Quvondiqovna	

Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshdagi giperaktiv bolalarga ta'lim berishning pedagogik-psixologik usullari.....	110
<i>Jo'rayeva Nargiza Toirovna, Kamalova Sarvinoz</i>	
Blum taksonomiyasi asosida ilmiy kompetentlikni takomillashtirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	113
<i>Mustafayeva Nilufar Ulashovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi ovoz buzulishiga ega bolalar bilan guruhli mashg'ulotlarni tashkil qilish	117
<i>Umida O'tbasarova Mexmanovna, Maksudbekova Xovvajon Xamidbek qizi</i>	
Bolalar jamoasida do'stona munosabatlarni shakllantirishda rivojlanish markazlarida loyiha asosida o'qitish texnologiyasidan foydalanish usullari	121
<i>Quronova Ismigul Xolmurod qizi</i>	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarda innovatsion metodlar orqali o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish metodikasi.....	126
<i>Rustamova Davlatxon Toyirjon qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'limda tarbiyaviy faoliyatni tashkil etishning innovatsion modellari	131
<i>Sanayeva Surayyo Bobonazarovna</i>	
"Tibbiy radiologiya" fanini o'qitishda pedagogik muloqot orqali tanqidiy operativ muloqotni o'stirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	139
<i>Shukurova Sevara Ilhomovna</i>	
Improving High Jump Techniques	143
<i>Tajimbetov Anvar Tengelbayevich</i>	
Filologik va ijtimoiy-siyosiy fanlarda ta'lim jarayonining innovatsion metodlari.....	146
<i>Yuldasheva Dilnoza Bekmurodovna</i>	
Понятие логического мышления и его особенности у младших школьников.....	149
<i>Ахмаджонова Нозима Нодиржон қизи</i>	
Интеграция психологии, обучения английскому языку, дошкольного образования и туризма: междисциплинарная модель формирующего опыта	152
<i>Омонуллаева Дилофуза Асадулла қизи</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning o'yin faoliyatida ijtimoiy motivlarni shakllantirish usullari.....	157
<i>Abduvaxobova Nodira</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda kognitiv faollikni rivojlantirishning afzalliklari.....	160
<i>Ismailova Nozima Umaraliyevna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini matni tahlil qilishga o'rgatishda zamonaviy yondashuvlarning ahamiyati.....	164
<i>Utanbayeva Dildora Abdixadirovna</i>	
Dorivor o'simliklar kursini o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirishda keys texnologiyalaridan foydalanish	168
<i>Mirzaboyev Timur Bisenbay o'g'li</i>	
Oliy ta'lim talabalarida ijtimoiy-axloqiy kompetensiyani rivojlantirish: empirik tadqiqot natijalari	171
<i>To'raqulov Akbar Rustam o'g'li</i>	
Gerontotexnologiya ijtimoiy-pedagogik innovatsiya sifatida	175
<i>Temirova Muyassar Abdulkarim qizi</i>	
O'quvchilarni ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalashda Sharq mutafakkirlarining qarashlaridan foydalanish	180
<i>Raximova Surayyo Otabek qizi</i>	
Yoshlarni kasb tanlashda ruhiy tayyorgarlik va shaxsiy qobiliyatlarni baholash.....	183
<i>Biysenov Temirbek Taumuratovich</i>	
Talabalarni ta'limiy qadriyatlar asosida pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorlash tizimini takomillashtirishning ahamiyati.....	188
<i>Choriyeva Surayyo Choriyevna</i>	
Differences Between Computer-Based and Paper-Based Assessment in Inclusive Education.....	192
<i>Davidova Sayyora Sirojiddin kizi</i>	
Raqamli muhit sharoitida ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiya jarayonining pedagogik modeli va tajriba-sinov natijalari.....	196
<i>Donayeva Nozimaxon Norbo'tayevna</i>	
Intellekt xarita yordamida o'quvchilarda "emotsional intellekt"ni rivojlantirish.....	201
<i>G'aniyev Abduqahhor Gadoyevich</i>	
Maktabgacha va kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarda o'yin faoliyatining psixologik-pedagogik ahamiyati.....	206
<i>Isayeva Mushtariy Alisher qizi</i>	
Umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasalarini innovatsion yondashuv asosida boshqarishning nazariy asoslari	210
<i>Mannanova Nargiza Xaydarovna</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Ingliz tilini o'rgatishda ona tilidan keng foydalanishning salbiy va ijobiy jihatlari215 Masharipova Kumushoy Amin qizi
	The Relationship Between Critical Thinking and Reading Comprehension in Primary School Students.....218 Mavlonova Dildora Shukhrat kizi
	Tasviriy san'at mashg'ulotlarida zamonaviy metodlardan foydalanish222 N. K. Musayeva, U. O. Ziyatova
	Singapurning ta'lim falsafasi: korporativ madaniyatni ma'naviy-ma'rifiy rivojlanish bilan integratsiyalash ...226 Nishonov Xayrulla Xolmirzaevich
	The Anthropocentric Paradigm in Modern Linguistics: Cognitive Linguistics and Linguacultural Studies in The Study of Language, Consciousness, and Culture230 Rajabova Shaxlo Shodmonovna
	Bugungi globallashuv davrida ta'lim tizimini rivojlantirish va uning sifatini oshirishda nostandart yondashuvning ahamiyati234 Ramazonova Salomat Saidovna
	Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini kreativ sinflar ishini tashkil etishga tayyorlash238 Saidova Gulruh Halim qizi
	O'zbek oilalarida ota-ona va farzand munosabatlarini tashxis qilishning psixologik xususiyatlari (Farg'ona vodiysi misolida).....242 Turg'unboeva Azizaxon G'ulomovna
	Сущность и специфика развития билингвизма у детей дошкольников246 Истамова Нигора Азимжановна
	Zamonaviy rahbarning innovatsion boshqarish texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning afzalliklari249 Xakimova Dildora Mashrabjonovna
	Креативный подход к развитию лингвометодического мышления студентов-филологов253 Ходжаниязова Айгуль Айтмуратовна
	Umumta'lim maktablarida tarbiya darslarini tashkil etish ijtimoiy zarurat sifatida257 Rashidova Gulnoza G'ulomovna
	Pedagogik risklarni boshqarishning nazariy asoslari va globallashuv jarayonidagi ahamiyati261 Xaydarov Sulaymon Amirqulovich
	Xronotop nazariyasiga tahliliy yondoshuvlar va qarashlar.....265 Avazov Vahabjon Tolibjon o'g'li
	Ko'zi ojiz bolalarning rus tili darslarida nutqiy kompetensiyasini shakllantirishning psixopedagogik asoslari268 Abduraximov Asror Sultonali o'g'li
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kasblar haqida dastlabki tasavvurlarni shakllantirishning psixologik-pedagogik asoslari.....271 Adizova Nilufar Quvondiq qizi
	Zamonaviy media texnologiyalarini ta'lim jarayoniga qo'llashning zarurati274 Alimov Asadulla Urokbayevich
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolaning rivojlanishida ijtimoiy muhitning ta'siri278 Alimova Umida Jumaboy qizi
	Kognitiv yondashuv asosida tibbiyot oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalari grammatik va diskursiv kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning nazariy modeli va pedagogik texnologiyasi.....282 Dadadjanova Feruza Muhammadyusupovna
	Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim texnologiyalarining rivojlanish tarixi va ommalashuvi.....286 Hojiyeva Maftuna Ulug'bekovna
	Bo'lajak boshlang'ich ta'lim o'qituvchilarida raqamli resurslardan foydalanish orqali adabiy kompetensiyani rivojlantirish289 Islomova Xafiza Azamatovna
	Ona tili o'qitish metodikasi fanidan mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etish.....293 Ismadiyorova Nafisaxon Ibroximjon qizi
	Axloqshunoslikning global muammolari va texnikaviy muhitning inson hayotiga ta'siri.....298 Kozimova Nargiza Istam qizi
	Ichki ishlar organlari xodimlarida kasbiy kompetentlikni oshirish va baholash usullarining xalqaro tahlili303 Mamatqulova Sanobar Ismatillayevna, Eshmurzayev Yigitali Shokirovich, Kadirova Durdonaxon Rustamovna
	Tabiiy fanlarda bilingval ta'lim va CLIL yondashuv309 Mannobxonova Muqaddamxon O'ktamxon qizi

Kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishda pragmatik muammolar va ularning yechimlari	313
Maxmudova Nigoraxon Boyqo'zi qizi	
Poshshoxo'ja Ibn Abdurahobxo'janing "Miftoh ul-adl" asaridagi pedagogik qarashlari.....	317
Muzaffarova Farida Muxtor qizi	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim jarayonida matn tushunishni shakllantirishda germenevtik metodlarning nazariy asoslari	321
Nazirova Shaxnoza Oдинаjon qizi	
Axborot iste'moli madaniyatini rivojlantirishda raqamli gigiyena va internet xavfsizligi.....	324
Ramazonov Jahongir Djalolovich	
Informatika fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy yondashuvlar	328
Sadinov Otabek Vaxodirovich	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarning ijtimoiylashuvida musiqa fanining ta'siri.....	332
Shahobiddinova Zilola Orif qizi	
Madaniy-ijtimoiy va ta'limiy omillarning bolalarning aqliy rivojlanishiga ta'siri	335
Shirinov Otabek Tuvlovich	
Tadqiqot metodi vositasida o'quvchilarda tabiiy-ilmiy savodxonlikni rivojlantirish.....	338
Suyarov Kusharbay Tashbayevich	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kommunikativ kompetensiyasi va nutq madaniyati.....	342
Saipova Hilola Abduhamitovna	
"Ekologik ochiq o'yinlar" 5–7 yoshli bolalar uchun.....	346
Tangirov Zoir Xo'jakulovich	
Yuqori malakali taekvondochilarni o'ziga xos genetik xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda sport seleksiyasi.....	350
Tursunaliyev Ulug'bek Shavkatjon o'g'li	
Musiqa maktabi o'quvchilarida madaniy qadriyatlar va ustoz-shogird an'alarining uzluksiz rivojlanishi ..	353
Seytanov Bayrambay	
Imom Buxoriyning "Al-Jome' as-sahih" asari talabalarda ma'naviy-axloqiy qadriyatlarni shakllantirish omili sifatida	356
Abduhalimova Nigora	
O'quvchilarning nutqiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda AKT vositalaridan foydalanishning metodik asoslari.....	359
Abdullayeva Zarnigor Usubjon qizi	
Коммуникативная компетентность и культура общения преподавателей начальных классов	364
Арысланбаева Анора Бердаховна	
Проблемы методической подготовки учителей в развитие дискурсивной компетенции по РКИ у учащихся уровня В1 средних общеобразовательных школ Узбекистана	366
Набиева Зарнигор Муминжон кизи	
"Tarbiya" darslari orqali o'quvchilarda huquqiy savodxonlikni rivojlantirish.....	369
Atamuradov Xasan Yuldoshevich	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining inklyuziv ta'limga tayyorgarligi: pedagogik va psixologik asoslari	374
Baxromova Guljamol Dilshodjon qizi	
Tajriba metodlari orqali maktab o'quvchilarida tabiat hodisalarini bashorat qilish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish.....	378
Baxtiyor Imanov, Begali Xoliqnazarov	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarning tashkillashtiruvchi-boshqaruvchilik kompetentligini shakllantirishning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari.....	384
Japparbergenova Indira Bayramovna	
Integrativ yondashuv asosida biologiya fanidan olimpiada masalalarini yechish metodikasi.....	387
Jumanov Muratbay Arepbaevich, Raxmatov Uchkun Ergashevich	
Darslarni tashkil qilishda 4K modelini qo'llash imkoniyatlari.....	393
Kadirov Tulkin Baxridinovich	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga tasviriy faoliyatning noodatiy usullarini o'rgatish metodikasi.....	397
Maxmudova Nasiba Nurmuxammetovna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida funksional savodxonlik tushunchasini ilmiy-pedagogik asoslash masalalari.....	406
Mirzaliyeva Gulhayo Abdulazizovna	

So'rovga asoslangan ta'lim texnologiyasining bosqichlari va qo'llash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish	410
Orifjonova Iroda Orifjon qizi, Ochilova Mehrubon Suratovna	
Dermatovenerologiya fanini CASC (Critisize, Analyze, Summarize, Conclude) modeli orqali o'qitish va uning talabalar klinik kompetentligini oshirishdagi o'rni	415
Po'latov Boburbek Ta'lat o'g'li	
Sport faoliyatida stress holatini tadqiq etishning nazariy asoslari.....	419
Ruzmatova Nigina Shotilla qizi	
Bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyachilarini kreativlikni rivojlantirish metodikasini takomillashtirish.....	422
Uchqunova Adiba Roziq qizi	
7-sinf adabiyot darslarida nutqni rivojlantiruvchi o'quv topshiriqlari tahlili.....	427
Umurova Farangiz Askarboy qizi	
O'zbek tilida fe'l birikmalarining pragmatik funksiyalari va ularning ingliz tili bilan qiyosi	430
Xudoynazarova Dildora Shonazar qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	433
Zayniddinova Mahzuna Baxtiyorovna	
Фольклор и время: формирование речевых навыков у детей начальной школы	439
Ниязова Хилола	
Xalq o'yinlari – jismoniy va ma'naviy tafakkur omili	443
Turg'unoy Ahmadjonovna Egamberdiyeva, Ergashoy Valijonovna Salimjon qizi	
Использование проектной деятельности для формирования языковой компетенции	446
Чаршамова Мехрийбан Уразбаевна	
Farzandlarni kelajak kasblariga tayyorlash.....	449
Hamroyeva Komila Axmatovna	
Talabalar analitik kompetentligini analitik-diaagnostik pedagogik metodlar orqali takomillashtirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari.....	455
Batirov Kamoliddin Zuhriddinovich	
Universal ta'limiy faoliyatlar: shaxsga xos universal ta'limiy faoliyatlar	458
Abdullayev A'zimjon Abduvali o'g'li	
Kasbiy motivatsiya – bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning raqobatbardoshligini shakllantirish omili	461
Melikova Elnora Shuxratovna	
Shaxsning kompetentligi va uni shakllantirish omillari.....	465
Usmonova Dilobat Elmurodovna	
“Nutq o'stirish metodikasi” fanining didaktik asoslarini takomillashtirish.....	469
Davlatova Ra'no Haydarovna	
Межэтническое взаимодействие в культурных координатах Востока и Запада: нормы, ценности, модели поведения.....	473
Айдарова Диана Смутуллаевна	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari tarbiyalanuvchilarining nutq ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarning o'rni	481
Abdumajitova Sayyohat Abduqosimovna	
Tibbiyot ta'limida talabalarning kommunikativ va tashkiliy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning integrativ yondashuvi va baholash mexanizmlari	484
Abduraimov Abbosbek Odiljon o'g'li	
Talabalarga ingliz tilini o'qitishda virtual reallikdan foydalanishning innovatsion tizimi.....	488
Alimova Maftuna Ravshanbek qizi	
Mustaqil O'zbekiston sharoitida rezerv va zahiradagi ofitserlar tayyorlash tizimining dolzarbligi.....	491
Aliyorov Alijon Bo'rievich, Teshaboyev To'liqinboy Yoqubovich	
Ekologik barqarorlikka erishishda ekologik ta'lim va tarbiyaning ahamiyati hamda O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimidagi holati.....	496
Bahodirjon Omonov	
Ona va bola o'rtasidagi psixologik munosabatlar tizimida nevrotik holatlarning shakllanishi	500
Bekmirov Tolib Rashidovich	
Effectiveness of Forming a Tolerant Thinking in Future Social Work Specialists	504
Ergashev Ikhtiyor Bakhtiyor ugli	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim yo'nalishi professor-o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarning o'rni.....	507
Fazlidjanova Nilufar Xikmatovna	

Indicators and Diagnostic Approaches for Dyslexia in Primary School Students.....	510
<i>Gaziyeva Saida Turgunovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshdagi bolalarda diqqat va xotirani rivojlantirish metodlari	514
<i>Jo'rayeva Nargiza Toirovna, Kamalova Sarvinoz</i>	
Ona tili darslarida esse yozish orqali kreativ fikrlashni shakllantirishning samarali metod va usullari.....	517
<i>Kabulov Inamjan Sharipbayevich</i>	
O'quvchi yoshlarning hayotiy maqsadlarini shakllantirish bo'yicha yondashuvlar	521
<i>Karimova Saida O'ktamovna</i>	
O'quvchilar ovozini rivojlantirishda qo'shiq kuylash malakalarini shakllantirishning ahamiyati	526
<i>Karshiyeva Diyora Abduxakim qizi</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalari va ularning dasturchilar tayyorlashdagi o'rni.....	532
<i>Mastonov Jahongir Mamatqul o'g'li</i>	
Zamonaviy asarlar tanlashning pedagogik va didaktik asoslari.....	535
<i>Musaboyeva Zulfira Iqboljon qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining elektron didaktik ta'minotini rivojlantirish metodikasi	541
<i>Narbayev Farrux Sharafbayevich</i>	
Mentorlik asosida yoshlarning ijtimoiy-pedagogik moslashuvi yuzasidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlar tahlili.....	548
<i>Nazarova Nigora Ravshanovna</i>	
Zamonaviy baholash texnologiyalarining o'quvchilar motivatsiyasiga ta'siri	551
<i>Norova Nilufar Norbo'ta qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining mantiqiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning elektron metodikasi.....	555
<i>Olimov Bahriddin Jalol o'g'li</i>	
Tanqidiy fikrlash va 4K kompetensiyalarining pedagogik-psixologik mohiyati	560
<i>Qizlarxon Azizova</i>	
Ona tilida so'z turkumlari va ularni ajratish tamoyillari.....	565
<i>Shadmankulova Dilyarom Xalikovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida inklyuziv ta'limni rivojlantirish.....	569
<i>Shodiyeva Dilnoza Qodirovna</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining kreativlik kompetentligini rivojlantirishni o'rganish – pedagogik muammo sifatida	572
<i>Toshpo'latova O'g'iloy Abdurahmon qizi</i>	
Inklyuziv ta'limda o'qituvchilarning roli va tayyorgarligi.....	576
<i>Xasanova Iroda Ikromjon qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak tasviriy san'at o'qituvchilarida kompozitsiyaga oid kompetensiyalarini rivojlanirish	580
<i>Xasanova Munisa Ziyodillo qizi</i>	
Влияние природы, количества, дисперсности и технологии введения наполнителя на свойства композиционных материалов	584
<i>Алимбаев Айбек Байрамович</i>	
STEM ta'limi va sun'iy intellekt: Qoraqalpog'iston maktablari uchun integratsiya hamda amaliy bo'lim	586
<i>Jumamuratov Perdebay Tileubayevich</i>	
Интерактивный метод как средство активизации всех учащихся на уроках родного языка	589
<i>Тажбенова Дина Куанышовна</i>	
Эффективность цифровых технологий в системе образования Узбекистана.....	591
<i>Усмонова Фируза Муродовна</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim muhitida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda jamoada ishlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish metodikasi ...	595
<i>Yo'ldosheva Mohidil Sobirjon qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalarining kasbiy kompetensiyasini innovatsion yondashuv asosida rivojlantirishning pedagogik zarurati	599
<i>Qurbonova Muxayyo Oltiboyevna</i>	
Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiy merosi, jadid maktablarining g'oyaviy asoslari va ta'limdagi modernizatsiya yo'nalishlari	602
<i>Mirzoyeva Nigora Shavkatjonovna, Abdisamatov Ozodbek</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda nutq rivojlanishini takomillashtirish metodlari.....	605
<i>Nishonova Ra'noxon Abdullojon qizi</i>	
Borrowed Proper Nouns in English and Uzbek: a Comparative Analysis.....	608
<i>Amirqulova Feruza Abdurashidovna</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Ingliz tilini o'qitishda autentik videolarning amaliy samaradorligi.....	613
	Dusmurodova Iroda Quvonovna	
	Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari samaradorligini ta'minlashda direktor va pedagog xodimlarning hamkorlikdagi faoliyati.....	616
	Olimjonova Odina Hasanxon qizi	
	Boshqaruv psixologiyasi terminlarini tarjima qilish muammolari va ularni hal qilish yo'llari.....	620
	Dilafuz Norboyeva	
	"Kommunikativ kompetensiya" tushunchasining xorijiy va milliy manbalarda talqini: qiyosiy tahlil.....	624
	G'ulomova Begoyim Elmurod qizi	
	Ijtimoiy tarmoqlardagi jinsiy jinoyatlarning psixologiyistik tomonlari	627
	Rahimqulova Lobar Hamro qizi	
	К вопросу обучения местоимению в корейском языке	631
	Мухиддинова Малика Батировна	
	The Importance and its Development Models of Critical Thinking	634
	Khasanova Shokhista Mirzaakhmad kizi	
	Gipertoniya kasalligining rivojlanishida sotsio-emotsional intellektning ta'siri	639
	Alimirzayev Nodirbek Avazbek o'g'li	
	Integratsiyalashgan va interaktiv yondashuvlar orqali o'qish tushunishini o'rgatish.....	643
	Aliqulova Mohinur	
	Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida direktorlarning shaxsiy kasbiy fazilatlarini shakllantirish.....	647
	Choriyeva Durdona Anvarovna, Ravshanova Noila	
	Didactic Potential of Innovative Methods in Teaching Biophysics Module	652
	Choriyeva Mahfuza Sadriddinovna	
	Notiqlik mahoratini rivojlantirishning tarixiy pedagogik ildizlari	657
	Ismoilov Usmonjon Baxramjon o'g'li	
	Kartografiya darslarini zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari bilan boyitish yo'llari.....	660
	Jololdinov Asror Toshtemirovich	
	Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarining kichik guruh tarbiyalanuvchilariga yo'l harakati turlari bo'yicha xavfsizlik talablarini o'rgatish.....	664
	Jumayev Yunus Rashidovich	
	Texnika yo'nalishidagi talabalarini ingliz tilini multimedia asosida o'qitishda o'quv modullarini loyihalash...	670
	Maxmudova Shaxnozaxon Odiljon qizi	
	Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni sun'iy intellekt vositalaridan foydalanish jarayonida tanqidiy fikrlashga o'rgatish	674
	Mirzayev Akramjon O'ktamjonovich, Sobirova Munavvarxon Qaxramonjonovna	
	Tajovvuz emotsiyasini tafsiflovchi fe'llar	677
	Normaxmatova Feruza Ruziboyevna	
	O'z-o'zini nazorat qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda interfaol metodlardan foydalanish usullari	681
	Otegenov Berdibay Menglibaevich	
	Texnika yo'nalishi talabalarining kasbiy kompetensiyalarini avtomatlashtirilgan loyihalash tizimlari asosida rivojlantirish muammolari	684
	Pozilova Shaxnoza Xaydaraliyevna, Xolmirzayeva Gulchehra Tulanovna	
	Faoliyatli yondashuvning nazariy asoslari: talabalar nutqiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishda zamonaviy metodologik tamoyillar.....	689
	Qurbonova Gulmira Alisher qizi	
	Maktab o'quvchilarida xalqaro baholash dastur talablari asosida hayotiy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishning nazariy asoslari	693
	Radjapov Ruslanbek Sarsenovich	
	Raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalari yordamida bo'lajak fizika o'qituvchilarining ijodiy-intellektual kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	697
	Shoyzakova Hilola Yusuf qizi	
	Talabalar ehtiyojlari va qobiliyatlari asosida oliy ta'limda differensial yondashuvni amalga oshirish strategiyalari	701
	Sultonova Farangiz Alisherovna	
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning ma'naviyatini oshirishda kitobxonlikni keng targ'ib qilish	706
	Usmanova Maxfuza	
	Talabalarda axloqiy qadriyatlarni singdirishning pedagogik asoslari	709
	Xolov Olimjon Chorshamiyevich	

Iqtidorli o'quvchilar bilan ishlashda tafakkurni rivojlantiruvchi o'yinlardan foydalanish metodikasi.....	712
<i>Ziyomiddinova Nilufar Avazbekovna</i>	
Влияние социальных сетей на формирование мировоззрения учащихся младшего подросткового возраста.....	716
<i>Ибрагимова З. И.</i>	
Bo'lajak muhandislarni kasbiy rivojlantirish metodikasi	720
<i>Axmedov Juraboy Raxmonberdiyevich</i>	
Oliy ta'lim talabalarida ma'naviy-axloqiy madaniyat samaradorligini oshirishda jadid pedagogik merosining o'rni	725
<i>Raxmatova Dilbar Anvar qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish usullari	730
<i>Xaitova E'zozaxon Baxrom qizi</i>	
Sun'iy intellektdan foydalanib bo'lajak texnologiya fani o'qituvchilarini innovatsion faoliyatga tayyorlash mexanizmlari	734
<i>Nurmamatov Zuxriddin Shavkat o'g'li</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshidagi bolalarning ijtimoiy-hissiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishda nutq o'stirish faoliyatining o'rni	737
<i>Toshpulatova Nargiza Abduraimovna</i>	
Xalq og'zaki ijodi orqali bolalarga tabiatni asrash va unga g'amxo'rlik munosabatlarini shakllantirish usullari	741
<i>Bo'riyeva Fayyoza Baxodirovna</i>	
Maktab ta'limida o'quv tadqiqot ishlarini tashkil etish – pedagogik muammo sifatida	745
<i>Jurayeva Umida Yuldashевна</i>	
Texnologiya o'qituvchilarining professional kompetentligini shakllantirish texnologiyasi	748
<i>Qalandarova Urinposhsha Yuldashovna</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim vositalari yordamida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kognitiv qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish ..	752
<i>Xodiyeva Nilufar Sherzod qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining kreativlik kompetentligini rivojlantirishni o'rganish – pedagogik muammo sifatida.....	756
<i>Toshpo'latova O'g'iloy Abdurahmon qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak biologiya o'qituvchilari kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishda amaliy mashg'ulotlarning didaktik imkoniyatlari	759
<i>Pardaeva Matonat Salimovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda nutqni rivojlantirish orqali emotsional intellektni shakllantirish	764
<i>Omonillayeva Maxfuza Ilyosjon qizi</i>	
Основные научные подходы различных учёных об организации самостоятельной работы студентов	768
<i>Чернова Татьяна Алексеевна</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim yo'nalishi professor-o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarning o'rni	772
<i>Fazlidjanova Nilufar Xikmatdjanovna</i>	
Ta'lim muassasalarida jismoniy madaniyat ta'limi samaradorligiga erishishda zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanish	775
<i>Xolikov Akmal Tajidinovich</i>	
Oliy ta'limda korrupsiyaga qarshi kurashish va uni oldini olish.....	778
<i>Axmedova Dilnora Kobiljonovna</i>	
Психологическая устойчивость к стрессу: опыт и открытия в Узбекистане	781
<i>Туракулова Дурдона Боходировна</i>	
Virtual ta'lim sharoitida bo'lajak geografiya o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetensiyasini shakllantirishda samaradorlikni oshirish	784
<i>Tajibayeva Xurshida Djumamuratovna, Pirmanov Mansur Qadiryevich</i>	
Развитие иноязычной межкультурной компетенции студентов в системе профессионально ориентированного языкового образования: роль паремий в формировании межкультурной коммуникации	788
<i>Амануллаева Камола Муминовна</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti tarbiyalanuvchilarining nutqini o'stirishda innovatsion metodikalarni qo'llash tendensiyasi.....	794
<i>Erhanova Nasiba Absayitovna</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Akademik ijro mahoratini rivojlantirishda xavaskor xor rahbarlar uchun zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlar 797 Yuldosheva Sadoqat Iloxomjonovna Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning nutq rivojlanishida zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanishning me'yoriy-huquqiy asoslari 801 Djamolova Noila Zayniddinovna Ta'lim va tarbiya jarayonida ulug' mutafakkirlarning odob va axloqga oid ilmiy merosidan foydalanishning o'ziga xos jihatlari 807 Ergasheva Dilnoza Mamasharifovna Tayyorlov guruh bolalarini kreativ qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishning innovatsion texnologiyalari 810 G'afforova Hurriyat Yangiboyevna Bo'lg'usi o'qituvchilarni media ta'limdan foydalanishga o'rgatish 814 G'aniyeva Sayyora Saidmurod qizi Bo'lajak pedagog kadrlarning boshqaruv kompetentligini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari 817 Jalolova Feruza Mirkamol qizi Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilar ijodiy tafakkurini rivojlantirish muammolari va yechimlari 822 Jumayev Xushboq Soatmumin o'g'li Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kasb motivlari barqarorligiga guruhii jipslikning ta'siri 827 Jumayeva Malika Aliyevna Jismoniy tarbiya darslari jarayonida maktab yoshidagi bolalarning jismoniy sifatlarini rivojlantirish 831 Kamardinov Baxtiyor Kamardinovich, Azimqulova Shaxlo Baxtiyor qizi Maktab va oila hamkorligida boshlang'ich ta'lim o'quvchilarini she'r yodlash qobiliyatini shakllantirish 837 Karimova Shoxsanam Islomovna Turkistondagi jadidchilik harakatining o'ziga xosligi va maktablardagi ta'lim tizimi 840 Karimova Zarrina Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari boshqaruvida ijobiy ijtimoiy munosabatlar muhitini shakllantirishdagi tashqi ta'sirlar 843 Maryam Raximova Tarbiya ijtimoiy-madaniy hodisa sifatida: an'anaviy qadriyatlar va zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlar uyg'unligi 848 Muhammadiyeva Feruza To'raikulovna From Access to Success: Advancing Inclusive Education in Universities 852 Nutfiyeva Dildora Bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyachilarini kasbiy tayyorgarligining pedagogik mexanizmlari 856 O'tasheva Lola Shoto'rayevna Kognitiv yondashuv asosida ixtisoslashtirilgan maktab o'quvchilarida ingliz tilini tushunish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish samaradorligini o'rganish 859 Qudratova Sultonposhsha Otabek qizi Klinik amaliyotda tibbiyot talabalarining stressni boshqarish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning innovatsion metodlari 864 Sobirov Qobuljon G'ofirjon o'g'li Ingliz tilini ikkinchi xorijiy til sifatida o'qitishda leksik derivatsiyalarning ahamiyati 868 Abdusattarov Mavlon Sherali o'g'li Tasavvuf adabiyotining paydo bo'lish omillari 872 Ahmadova Shohsanam Sodiq qizi Ichki ishlar akademiyasi kursantlarining favqulodda vaziyatlarda qaror qabul qilish jarayonini takomillashtirishning nazariy metodologik asoslari 875 Kadirova Sayyora Madaminovna Maktab fizika kursini o'qitishda ekologik tarbiyani shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari 878 Karimov Abdurahmonjon Ma'rufjon o'g'li Til o'rgatishda zamonaviy usullardan foydalanishning samaradorligi va joriy etish strategiyalari 882 Muxammadjonova Nafisa Rustam qizi O'quvchilarning fizika faniga oid umumiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda elektron va mobil ta'lim platformalaridan foydalanishning didaktik imkoniyatlari 885 Najmiddinova Murat Kamolovich Sun'iy intellekt asosida talabalarining falsafiy tafakkurini rivojlantirishning metodologik asoslari 890 Nodirbekov Furqatbek Umarjon o'g'li
-------------------------------------	--

Jadidlarning milliy ta'lim paradigmasi asosida OTM talabalarida milliy identlikni (o'zlik) rivojlantirish.....	894
<i>Ortiqboyev Soxibjon Inomjon o'g'li</i>	
Shifokor shaxsini tarbiyalashda empatiya va axloqiy qadriyatlarining o'rni.....	897
<i>Tajiboyeva Odinaxon Rustamjon qizi</i>	
Features of Flipped Learning to Improve Speaking Proficiency	901
<i>Tojiyeva Matluba Mahmud kizi</i>	
Socio-Cultural Approach to Teaching English to Students of Economic Specialties	904
<i>Xamdamova Nilufar Esanovna</i>	
Pedagogik mahorat	908
<i>Zakirova Dilfuza Ergashboyevna</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning kasbiy shaxsiy sifatlarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari.....	912
<i>Xabilova Sitora Tursunmurod qizi, Payg'amova Husnida</i>	
Korpus asoslangan til pedagogikasini yuqori kurs ingliz tili ta'limiga joriy etishning nazariy jihatlari.....	915
<i>Toshpulatova Mexriniso Kilichevna</i>	
Bo'lajak muhandislarni kasbiy rivojlantirishni pedagogik muammo sifatida o'rganish.....	919
<i>Axmedov Juraboy Raxmonberdiyevich</i>	
Talabalarning bilim o'zlashtirish darajasi va faolligini oshirishda differensial yondashuvning ahamiyati	925
<i>Sultonova Farangiz Alisherovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili darslarida o'quvchilarning yozuv malakasini oshirish yo'llari	929
<i>Boltayeva Barno Isakulovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida tarbiyalanuvchilarni milliy ruhda tarbiyalash metodikasini rivojlantirish.....	932
<i>Qosimova Aziza Umarali qizi</i>	

SOCIO-CULTURAL APPROACH TO TEACHING ENGLISH TO STUDENTS OF ECONOMIC SPECIALTIES

Xamdamova Nilufar Esanovna

Doctoral student,
Gulistan State University (Uzbekistan)

Abstract: This article examines the significance of cultural awareness in the process of foreign language acquisition, emphasizing the necessity of understanding the culture of the target language community. It also explores the key components of the socio-cultural approach to the development of oral communication skills.

Key words: language, religion, social behavior, critical cultural awareness, intercultural barriers.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada xorijiy tilni o'rganish jarayonida madaniy ongning ahamiyati yoritilgan bo'lib, maqsad til jamiyati madaniyatini anglash zarurligi ta'kidlanadi. Shuningdek, og'zaki nutq ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda sotsio-madaniy yondashuvning asosiy jihatlari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: til, din, ijtimoiy xulq-atvor, tanqidiy madaniy ong, madaniyatlararo to'siqlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается значение культурной осведомлённости в процессе изучения иностранного языка, подчёркивается необходимость понимания культуры сообщества целевого языка. Также анализируются ключевые компоненты социокультурного подхода к развитию устных коммуникативных навыков.

Ключевые слова: язык, религия, социальное поведение, критическое культурное сознание, межкультурные барьеры.

INTRODUCTION

Amid the current processes of globalization, the role of foreign language acquisition in the professional education of economics students has become increasingly prominent. Particular emphasis is placed on mastering the language within the framework of intercultural dialogue, as proficiency is now regarded as a critical competency for effective international and cross-cultural communication.

In professional communication across national and cultural boundaries, individuals inevitably engage with diverse cultural traditions and behavioral patterns shaped by distinct mentalities. As such, language cannot be separated from culture; it is embedded within socially transmitted norms, values, and practices that define the lifestyle of a given linguistic community. Language functions as both a product and a symbol of culture, inherently reflecting its underlying structures and meanings.

Given this interdependence, it is pedagogically sound to structure foreign language instruction for philology students within the framework of a socio-cultural approach. A core tenet of this approach involves teaching communicative competence through the lens of intercultural dialogue. This perspective fosters an understanding of one's own cultural identity as viewed through the lens of another, facilitating the development of critical cultural distance. Such reflective engagement, described as a "micro-dialogue in consciousness," enables learners to reconsider their self-perception, identity, and their intermediary position between native and target cultures.

Moreover, the principle of foreign language instruction through the lens of a dialogue of cultures—central to the socio-cultural approach—entails an ideologically informed orientation that facilitates the reduction of communicative barriers within intercultural contexts. These barriers are understood as challenges that emerge during cross-cultural interaction and hinder communicative effectiveness. Scholars attribute the origin of such barriers to discrepancies in the cognitive frameworks employed by individuals from different cultural backgrounds, including variations in verbal and non-verbal communication systems, as well as ideologies shaped by

specific socio-historical contexts. Accordingly, the socio-cultural approach not only enhances students' linguistic competencies but also fosters their cultural and personal development. It promotes an openness to otherness, encourages the recognition of alternative worldviews and identities, and supports the learner's progression toward a more advanced level of intercultural awareness and self-reflection.

Intercultural communication serves as a foundational reference point in foreign language learning, facilitating the comprehension of native speakers' behavioral patterns, cultural and historical contexts, and realia, thereby enabling more effective engagement with members of other cultural communities. This process entails not only acquiring knowledge of the customs, traditions, worldviews, and artistic expressions of the target language culture, but also fostering openness to alternative mentalities and readiness for intercultural interaction. Mastery of both verbal and non-verbal communicative codes is essential, as it contributes to overcoming ethnocentrism manifested in the negative evaluation of cultural "others," the reinforcement of stereotypes, and the persistence of cultural prejudices. Through sustained intercultural engagement, learners are introduced to the value systems of foreign cultures and become acquainted with the culturally specific rituals that govern both verbal and non-verbal behavior. Given the differing levels of significance attributed to certain behavioral norms across cultures, such knowledge plays a critical role in enhancing the efficacy of intercultural communication.

Within the framework of the socio-cultural approach to foreign language instruction, language and culture are treated as inseparable components of the learning process. This perspective not only emphasizes the development of communicative competence, but also integrates the study of cultural norms, communicative models, value systems, symbolic representations, and characteristic features of national identity inherent to the target language community. Accordingly, the application of a socio-cultural approach is considered especially appropriate for the selection of instructional materials aimed at training highly qualified specialists in philology and linguistics.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The socio-cultural approach in foreign language teaching has been widely studied by leading scholars who emphasize the inseparable link between language and culture. Lev Vygotsky highlighted the interdependence of language and thought, stressing that social interaction plays a crucial role in cognitive development and language acquisition. Dell Hymes, through his theory of communicative competence, argued that language should be viewed not merely as a system of grammatical rules but as a social practice shaped by cultural norms and values. In this context, learners must acquire not only linguistic skills but also the ability to interpret and engage with the cultural framework of the target language community.

Contemporary researchers also underline the importance of this perspective. David Crystal examined the status of English as a global language and emphasized how its use across different cultural settings provides learners with valuable communicative experiences. Claire Kramsch further explored the dialectical relationship between language and culture, proposing that learners should be trained as "intercultural mediators" who can navigate multiple cultural identities. Uzbek scholars have also contributed to this field. For instance, Hamdamov E. E. demonstrated that the socio-cultural component plays a vital role in shaping the professional-linguistic competence of English language teachers, confirming the importance of integrating cultural awareness into language education. These findings indicate that the socio-cultural approach is an effective strategy for fostering not only linguistic proficiency but also intercultural communicative competence among students.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In conducting this research, data were obtained through the analysis of authentic educational resources, including textbooks, scholarly articles, and teaching materials that emphasize the integration of language and culture. Particular attention was given to the Global (Advanced level) coursebook by Lindsay Clandfield and Amanda Jeffries, which provided practical examples of socio-cultural content in language learning. Classroom observations and student feedback were also considered to assess the effectiveness of the socio-cultural approach in developing communicative competence. The collected materials were examined using qualitative content analysis, which enabled the identification of thematic structures, cultural components, and pedagogical strategies. This approach allowed for the evaluation of how socio-cultural elements contribute to students' linguistic and intercultural development.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

After examining a range of authentic educational resources, we selected the textbook Global (Advanced level) by Lindsay Clandfield and Amanda Jeffries for use in oral and written communication practice with third-year philology students. The materials presented in this course are notably original and contemporary,

with topics structured around cultural comparison and engagement with current global realities. The thematic content encourages critical reflection on cross-cultural issues and promotes awareness of pressing topics in the modern world, such as:

- Is Wikipedia part of a new global brain?
- The world's most adventurous museums
- Solar solutions
- Dialogue in the dark – an exhibition to discover the unseen
- Childhood toys
- Heroism and personal qualities
- Gender differences

These topics are devoted to the main problems of modern global society: the growing role of computers and the Internet in people's lives, the development of modern art, the search for alternative energy sources, the problems of people with disabilities, the upbringing and development of children, the formation of a person's personality, and relationships between men and women.

Of particular interest is the thematic structure of the textbook's units, which are organized around conceptual oppositions—such as Fact and Fiction, Light and Dark, Great and Small, Theory and Practice, and Heroes and Villains. This structural approach, in our view, fosters the development of students' critical thinking skills and stimulates active participation in classroom discussions, encouraging learners to articulate and defend their own viewpoints. Additionally, the course includes a dedicated section titled Function Globally, which focuses on the cultivation of both professional and interpersonal communication skills. This includes training in areas such as event organization, participation in discussions, conversational management, telephone communication, and decision-making. The integration of these components supports the development of communicative competence among philology students, equipping them for effective interaction within an intercultural environment.

The Global English section of the course features articles by renowned British philologist and linguist David Crystal, whose extensive research on the diversity of English dialects led him to propose the concept of a global standard for spoken English. Following the reading of these texts, students engage in tasks designed to enhance critical thinking and communicative competence. These activities often involve comparing linguistic phenomena in English with those of the learners' native language, which consistently stimulates student interest and fosters motivation for in-depth discussion.

The course also incorporates high-quality, authentic audio materials, including speech patterns, active vocabulary usage, mini-dialogues, and video content from the BBC, allowing students to hear a wide range of native English speakers. These include experts in philology, university students, everyday speakers, and even non-native speakers learning English as a second language. This diversity of voices provides learners with valuable exposure to different speech models and accents.

Overall, the Global course is structured to integrate linguistic and cultural content in a cohesive manner, with the explicit aim of familiarizing students with the mentality and worldview of the target language community. In doing so, it effectively supports the development of students' intercultural communicative competence.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, the integration of a socio-cultural approach in foreign language instruction for economy students proves to be an effective strategy for developing both linguistic proficiency and intercultural communicative competence. By treating language and culture as interdependent, this approach enables learners to engage critically with cultural values, communication norms, and worldviews different from their own. The use of the Global coursebook by Lindsay Clandfield and Amanda Jeffries illustrates the practical application of this method. Its thematically rich content, authentic materials, and emphasis on intercultural dialogue stimulate students' interest, promote critical thinking, and enhance their readiness for real-life communication in multicultural contexts. Thus, the socio-cultural approach not only supports the formation of highly qualified language professionals but also prepares them for meaningful participation in global communication.

References:

1. Esanovna, H. N. (2024). Sociocultural competence is the goal of using a sociocultural approach to teaching a foreign language. *Scientific Approach to the Modern Education System*, 3(25), 358–360.
2. Xamdamova, N. E. (2023). Some views on sociocultural theories in language acquisition. *Scientific Progress*, 4(3), 92–94.
3. Hamdamov, E. E. (2021). The content of the language professional-gnostic training of an English teacher. *Bulletin of Gulistan State University*, 2021(2), 35–41.
4. Hamdamov, E. E. (2021). Technology forming the gnostic competence of future teachers of foreign language. *Bulletin of Gulistan State University*, 2021(1), 50–55.
5. Ergashevich, H. E. (2022). Bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchisining kasbiy-gnostik kompetensiyasi va uning didaktik ahamiyati. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 25, 302–304. Retrieved from <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/378>
6. Ergashevich, K. E. (2024). Effective strategies for enhancing the professional-gnostic competency of aspiring foreign language teachers. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(5), 170–174.

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. №9

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.